

The Effect of Advertising on Increasing Sales of Food Products

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Abstract:

Reducing the consumption of unhealthy food is a major public health priority. Food marketing is part of the collateral environment that influences children's food preferences and diet. The food, beverage, and restaurant industries are the biggest individual product advertisers. As such, there is a large concern that advertising can lead to obesity, which may lead to various health problems. The food advertising that children are exposed to falls into two main categories. The first consists of food advertising, and the second consists of food product packaging, which includes television advertising as well as packages of food sold at the supermarket. Advertising is a major business expense that affects certain food

product sales. Well-targeted advertising helps to successfully promote food products. The main objective of any for-profit company, like any advertising campaign, is to create sales, and this study is directly interested in examining the impact that food advertising has on food sales. The main purpose of this paper is to determine the factors that more heavily affect the increase of sales of food products, taking into account that advertising has a positive influence.

Keywords: *Advertising, Sales, Food Products, technology, Iraq.*

Introduction

The development and progress in various commercial, industrial and service activities have opened wide areas for growth and penetration into the markets of many countries that were

previously unknown to various organizations. The great diversity of goods and services has also made it necessary to have an effective means linking the producer and the consumer, and this means is advertising, as it is one of the elements. The main and effective promotional mix is that

advertising does not only serve the product, but its benefit extends to include the distributor and the consumer. For the producer, it leads to increasing his profits, his fame, his continuation in the market, and facing the challenges of his competitors in the long term, i.e. maintaining his competitive position. For the distributor, it leads to a rapid turnover of his profits. As for the consumer, it is an educational and educational tool that helps him choose from among the many goods and services available in the market. (Hafez, 2010). As human thinking and culture have been affected by these changes, desires have multiplied and the ways and means of achieving and satisfying them have varied, and the need for advertising has emerged as a visual or audio means. Or read, affecting feelings and thoughts, it attracts attention and creates the desire to buy. Just as advertising works to win the consumer, guide him, and ensure his loyalty to the advertiser's goods, we also find that it represents an advanced line of defense towards competing goods through its contribution to the organization obtaining an appropriate market share, then maintaining this share and increasing sales. Given the increased interest in advertising activity in the recent period and the multiplicity of its methods and techniques, and its means and the fluctuation of the advertisements that we see, read and hear between success and failure, as well as in view of the essential role that advertising plays in increasing the sales of companies and working to ensure that these companies remain steadfast in the face of the various challenges they face. This research came to address this topic (the role of advertising in increasing the sales of food products). The first section: the problem, objectives, and importance of the research: Research problems, Main hypothesis: What is the role of advertising, specifically electronic advertising, in increasing the company's sales? And from him, the following problems can be derived: What is the role of advertising in increasing sales and enhancing the competitive position of the product? Does advertising have a role in building and changing consumers' point of view towards a commodity? Does advertising the product affect its image among consumers? To answer the previous problems, we put forward the

following hypotheses, which will be proven or disproven through what we reach. During the search. Advertising is considered the most important element that affects consumers' attitudes towards a commodity. Advertising has a major role in increasing the company's sales and enhancing the competitive position of the commodity.

Objectives

The objectives of the research can be summarized in the following, points:

- Identifying the concept of advertising, its types, and the objectives it seeks to achieve;
- Knowing the extent to which advertisements for goods and services influence consumer trends;
- Knowing the extent to which advertisements influence building the competitive position of goods and increasing sales.

The importance of this research lies in that it focuses on advertising as one of the important elements in building the competitive position of the commodity and increasing the volume of sales. This research addresses the role of advertising and its importance in changing consumer attitudes and persuading them, as well as building an image of the advertised commodity. As one of the powerful elements that change consumer trends. Knowing the strength of its influence on consumers' purchasing decisions regarding a commodity, the importance of research is evident in the points next:

- Its importance in helping departments responsible for advertising know the factors, methods and methods, The basic and correct methods for making a strong and effective advertisement.
- Achieving the desired goals, especially those related to increasing the organization's sales in a way that guarantees it, appropriate market share compared to its competitors.
- Directing and assisting the producer in achieving long-term impact advertising for his

products or services.

Theoretical Framework

Study of consumer behavior Consumer behavior: It is the group of mental and muscular activities associated with the process of evaluation, comparison, obtaining and using goods or services. (Al-Sayed 2008), due to the current technological development, the need to study consumer behavior has increased by Researchers and marketing officials have become increasingly interested in studying the consumer quantitatively and behaviorally and how he makes decisions related to directing the resources available to him of time, effort and money to purchase and consume goods and services in order to develop appropriate market strategies for their impact on the consumer In order to obtain and use where consumer behavior relates to goods and services, including making the purchase decision itself (Mohammed Farid Al-Sahn 2000), recent years have witnessed a noticeable interest in understanding the psychology of the consumer and the justifications for his behavior and predicting them as much as possible, looking at consumers as groups affected by each other, and paying attention to the change that occurs in Their behavior and determining the reasons for that change, and several factors combined to increase interest in studying consumer behavior, including its various advantages: and its various applications in the field of marketing strategy planning, and among these reasons are (Kurtel, 2010):

- 1) The spread and increased acceptance of the marketing concept as a philosophy for the organization. The marketing concept is based on a study of needs, the consumer and trying to satisfy it is the ultimate goal of the projects, and then the commodity and the various marketing strategies must be looked at from the point of view of the producers.
- 2) The high failure rate of many new products is due to poor planning of marketing strategies, Understand consumer behaviour, motivations and desires.
- 3) The increasing impact of environmental

variables, whether on organizations or individuals, as consumer protection movements and increased awareness.

Consumers organizing themselves into groups, in addition to the influence of government decisions, put great pressure on producers to take into account the desires and motives of consumers. Studying consumer behavior is essential because it helps the producer and marketer understand what the consumer is thinking and makes it easier for them to target him with their goods and services, thus building a strong competitive position and increasing the volume of sales, as the consumer is the basis of competition in the market. Studying consumer behavior also enables us to answer the following questions (Khalfawi, 2007):

- Are the products and services provided by the organization the ones that the consumer actually needs? Is the demand for the products provided by the organization increasing or decreasing?
- If demand is decreasing, what types of products or assortments must the organization obtain in order to be able to meet the consumer's desires and thus increase the volume of sales?

Answering these questions serves the organization and helps it adapt what it produces to the consumer's desires after the organization divides the market and determines Any market that it will target with its product will follow a specific strategy to determine its competitive position in the market, and this will help it achieve good profits.

The Concept of Competitive Position

The success of a marketing strategy for a commodity brand cannot depend on the procedures and methods of market segmentation that are implemented only, but rather it must be implemented. The marketing strategy to be applied must include all the processes and activities that lead to determining the marketing position (replacing the commodity or aligning the brand or commodity brands with the requirements and characteristics

of the target markets and the diverse segments of consumers they contain and under constantly changing environmental conditions (Obaidat, 2006).

The concept of positioning or determining competitive position falls between marketing and business strategy, and we will try to understand the term through the Where Kotler and Keller defined it as “the place that the product occupies in the minds of target consumers in relation to competing products, and determining competitive position includes placing the unique benefits of the brand in the minds of consumers” (Kotler & Keller, 2006).

Schiffman and Kanuk defined it as “Create an excellent image of the product or service in the mind of the consumer, and this image must be different from competing brands and satisfy needs and desires better than them.”) (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2007) Both definitions focus on the benefits inherent in the brand for goods or services.

Muhammad Obaidat defined it as: how target consumers perceive the marketing program for the commodity or brand under study compared to the sensory perceptions of other groups (or the same consumers of the first brand) of consumers and other competing brands. (Obaidat, 2012).

And Muhammad Abdel Azim Abu Al-Naga defined it as It is: how consumers perceive the important characteristics of the product, in other words, the space that the product occupies in the minds of consumers compared to other competing products. Both definitions focus on consumer perceptions and their impact on building a competitive position, meaning that this investigation is based on the impact on consumers’ perceptions of a good image of the product. That is, this definition is from the point of view of consumers (Azim, 2008) and from the point of view of the organization: Catherine Few explains that defining the position of the brand consists of giving it an original position in the minds of consumers and reserve customers, in order to distinguish it from competitors, and to match the decisive desires of the category.

Targeted Consumers

In light of this concept, determining the competitive position matches the wishes or beliefs of marketing officials, and the difference in positioning that the organization intends for a particular brand, or the consumer’s perception of the latter, may appear. (Suwaidan, 2009) Muhammad Farid Al-Sahn defined it as “the organization’s attempt to present the commodity in a way that distinguishes it from what competitors offer, so that it can gain a distinct competitive position in the market it serves.” (Al-Sahn 2010).

There are two characteristics that can be used to determine the organization’s strengths in relation to its competitive position, which are represented (Hali, 2011):

- 1) The organization’s share of the market: The greater the latter, the stronger its competitive position becomes, and thus the potential returns from future investments increase.
- 2) The large share of the market also contributes to achieving advantages at the level of experience curve economics, and this results in increased customer loyalty to the organization.

Uniqueness Factors

Both uniqueness and strength factors consider the number of distinct competencies of the organization as the second characteristic, The more difficult it is to imitate and imitate the organization's experience in the field of research and training, as well as its competitive position. Its skills in manufacturing and marketing, its knowledge of special customer segments and its distinguished reputation, the more distinguished the center, the organization's competitive advantage is strong, and this doubles the organization's returns from competitive strategy. Market share is also considered one of the basic indicators of competitive position, which shows the organization’s strength in the market in which it operates. Farhat and Amira point out, saying, “If the product, activity, or investment has a large market share, the organization can

achieve It generates a good cash flow from it and then uses that flow to promote and support new activities that have potential for new growth.” (Talib, & Al-Janabi, 2012).

The Concept of Advertising

A lot of specialized research, studies, and scientific writings in the field of marketing and advertising have revealed the existence of many advertising concepts, the most important of which can be explained as follows: Advertising is a communication process that aims to produce a specific effect, which is to convince the audience targeted by the with the advertised service (Zaki, 2001).

Advertising advertiser and push it to behavior. In which he offers to buy or deal is also defined as: It is the information at the time of the tempting and influential presentation of the good, service or idea through various means of advertising in order to follow the path of consumption that the advertiser and its producer are satisfied with in exchange for a paid fee that shows the identity of the advertiser (Muhammad, 2010). He also defined advertising as: “Any form of presenting ideas, goods, or services that are not personal and paid for by a specific, well-known advertiser” (Bellilou, 2011), as presented by Al-Zoubi.

There are many definitions we take from: Advertising is the art of definition. Advertising is a persuasive means of communication directed to the public about what is announced. Advertising is the means used to deliver the sales message. Advertising is also defined as every activity that disseminates information and data about goods and services with the intention of arousing the insight of consumers in identifying their needs and how to follow them, and in order to help producers acquire new customers by introducing these prospective customers to the goods and services.

The most widely accepted definition is that of the American Marketing Association, which defined advertising as “any form of non-personal presentation and promotion of ideas, goods, and services on behalf of a specific

person or entity” (Ghoneim, 2008).

Electronic Advertising

Internet advertising refers to all forms of promotional custom provided by a specific advertiser through the Internet (Qahf & Taha, 2006). It is defined as a communication process through publishing and broadcasting readable advertising messages, including the Internet, among the target audience in order to motivate them to purchase goods and services and persuade them to be convinced by those messages and take the appropriate decision regarding them (Al-Hilali, 2013).

Electronic advertising is also known as a method technical, persuasive, enticing presentation based on photographing products in three dimensions. This type is often used in technology-intensive digital products, but it is also used in advertising all types of products, especially those that respond more to the technologies presented, such as: computers, books, accessories, electrical and electronic devices, and others (with an inch of relation).

He defined it as: “It is a paid, non-personal means of communication that is followed by business companies, profit-making institutions, and individuals for the purpose of presenting goods, services, and ideas to a group of consumers or industrial buyers and convincing them of them.” (Al-Zoubi, 2016). Electronic advertising is advertising that promotes various goods and services via the Internet in a way that is creative and attractive to the consumer. (Fandoushi, 2012). Patterns of electronic advertising:

- Experimental pattern: The product is tested and tested, and then the decision to purchase is made. This method is of course available. This pattern provides the customer with the opportunity to deal with some goods and services.
- Type of content of procedural orientation towards the consumer: In this style, customers are provided with extensive information about the product so that they can compare and

contrast these products and choose the appropriate one that matches their needs and desires.

Electronic Advertising Methods

The goal of advertising is to define, influence, and persuade the audience, but to be effective it must be attractive and interesting. Advertisers use multiple methods to make advertising, which usually include: influential, effective, and - Attention-grabbing titles. Logos. And the characteristics of the commodity – characteristics- Compare goods. -Repetition. In general, advertisers present their message in a realistic or emotional way. The realistic method explains the nature of the advertised commodity, how to use it, and the way it was made. As for the emotional method, it resorts to methods that make the commodity gain personal satisfaction for the consumer. Advantages and disadvantages of electronic advertising: (Ahmed, 2009), Its advantages:

- It is a method of communication that combines mass and individuality, as it characterizes the communicative relationship between the advertiser and the recipient Interactive and sharing the future.
- Experimentality and freedom to search for information without imposing it on the recipient.
- The advertisement is on an international scale. The advertising message is easy to change or modify.
- The Internet is a cheap advertising method when compared to other means
- Internet advertising gives the advertising company a distinct marketing status and a desirable mental image.
- Internet advertisements often include a large amount of symbols, signs, and gestures, which adds a sophisticated technical dimension on the advertisement.
- Internet advertising is considered a direct response method.

- -The ability for interested consumers and buyers to learn about advertisements without time limits, allowing them to view them at any time.
- The possibility of displaying advertisements in clearer and more promotional ways, lack of standards and measurement methods, meaning it is difficult to measure the effect of advertising.
- Disadvantages of using it:
 - Difficulty in measuring market size, i.e. difficulty in estimating important matters.
 - The degree of frequency of user clicking on the advertisement is still weak, sales, it is a group of non-advertising techniques that work to excite consumers and push them to buy goods and the services offered to them. (Qahf & Taha 2006,).

It is all marketing activities through which a certain additional value can be added to the good or service produced by the organization for a specific period of time in order to appeal to the purchasing behavior of consumers and to increase the efficiency of distributors (Al-Sirafi, 2010).

Philip Kotler defines “sales” as a set of techniques directed to stimulate and encourage demand in the short term by increasing the volume of purchase of a specific product or service by consumers or commercial intermediaries. (Kotler et al., 2003)

Process Sales include the sum of immediate and targeted marketing activities characterized by the presentation and accompanying media aimed at creating new behaviors or strengthening existing behaviors for agents and brokers in the broad sense (buyer - seller) and contributing to increasing demand for the organization’s products) (Al-Nadi, 2011).

The American Marketing Association has defined the sales process as a group of important activities to promote the customer’s purchase of a product or service. The sales process can be completed in person, by phone, e-mail, or

through other means of communication (Al-Himyari, 2013).

Procedurally: It is a series of techniques that complement the selling and advertising process and that prompt the consumer to buy (Kurtle 2010).

Types of Sales Promotion Methods

Free Samples

These are units of produced goods that are provided to prospective consumers free of charge. They are provided either by mail or attached to another commodity. It is preferable to attach to the sample an explanatory leaflet showing how to use the commodity and its benefits. The method is one of the most effective sales promotion methods, despite its high cost. It is typically used to introduce a new item to the market and is commonly used by establishments that produce packaged goods, such as food and cosmetics. The most important criteria that must be met when using samples are:

- The products must be of low value.
- Dividing products into small items.
- Short product purchasing cycle.

Advantages of using free samples: (Mohamed Al-Sayrafi, 2010): a) Enticing the prospective buyer to try the product; b) Allowing the consumer to put the product on trial and thus carry out the evaluation process, which helps to reach a more rational purchasing decision.

Souvenirs

These are gifts provided by the organization to either the beneficiary of the service or the intermediaries, with the aim of forming each of good relations with them.

Promotional Gifts

It is with the institution and is given to the buyer to develop and increase his dealings. It is a reward given to the beneficiary in exchange for his dealings known to him before benefiting from the service (Alian, 2009).

Free Tasting

Some stores advertise a free tasting campaign inside their stores, where they provide tables with the ability for consumers to taste them. This method is usually used for goods, through which the product is displayed. New goods and goods that the consumer does not know (Al-Alaq & Al-Abdali, 2010).

Exhibitions

This method is considered one of the most important ways to stimulate sales because of the presentation materials it contains, as well as due to the public demand for it. Exhibitions contribute to achieving more than one purpose. In addition to stimulating sales, products are introduced in an integrated manner. (Alaa Hussein Al-Sarabi et al., 2011).

The scope of field research and its methodological procedures, Study population and sample

Our research population is mainly represented by consumers of foodstuffs manufactured in different factories, which is characterized by diversity and multiplicity. As for the selected sample, the purposive sample was chosen, which is defined as the sample in which the researcher intends to be from certain units in the belief that it best represents the original community, and thus obtaining results that are closer to the results reached by the researcher, as the purposive sample included 150 individual consumers, and with regard to the type of questions adopted in this questionnaire, they are almost closed questions in which the method of binary and triple options was relied upon, in accordance with the objectives of the research and the nature of the hypotheses.

Study Methodology

It is the strategy or general plan that the researcher draws in order to be able to solve the problem of his research or achieve his goal. It is a general plan that relies on foundations and rules to achieve the objectives of research or scientific work (Razzaq et al., 2005) There are those who define it as a method that the

researcher follows and through which he defines the concepts, the framework of the study, the research community, the diversity of the data required, its sources, and how to obtain it. (Imam, 2008). Scientific research has general fundamentals that impose on it a specific approach that may differ from the approach taken. It is followed in other topics, and for the purpose of answering the problem raised in our research, which revolves around the role of electronic advertising in increasing sales, the approach used in this research is the descriptive approach, as it depends on and expressing it qualitatively the study of the reality or phenomenon that exists in reality and is concerned with describing it accurately through describing the phenomenon with an explanation of its characteristics or a quantitative expression, which gives us a numerical description with an indication of the amount or size of this phenomenon and the degrees of its relationship with other phenomena. The descriptive method is also one of the most widely used methods in various scientific and humanitarian studies. The limits of the descriptive method are not limited to describing the phenomenon and collecting information. Rather, this information must be classified, organized, and expressed quantitatively or qualitatively in order to understand the relationship of this phenomenon with other phenomena. The goal of organizing and classifying information is to help the researcher reach conclusions and generalizations that contribute to understanding and developing reality.

It depends on the nature of the topic to be studied, in addition to the goal to be achieved, and since we are studying the role of advertising, Electronic help in increasing sales. In line with the topic, we have relied on the questionnaire form, which is one of the most popular tools. It is widely used in collecting data in research, and this is due to the advantages achieved by this tool, both in relation to. And the ease of processing its data statistically.

Table 1. The Distribution of Sample Members by Gender

Sex	Repetition	Percentage
Male	66	44%
Female	84	56%
Total	150	100%

From the students' achievement based on the questionnaire form, what is noticeable from the table presented regarding the nature of the sample members is that the percentage of females is greater than the percentage of males, where the percentage of females was 56%, while the percentage of males was 44%.

Table 2. The Distribution of the Sample According to Age

Age	Repetition	Percentage
18-24	135	90%
25-34	8	5,33%
35-44	3	2%
45 or more	4	2,67%
Total	150	100%

The table shows that the group most exposed to electronic advertisements is the group between 18 and 25 years old. With a percentage of 90%, which is equivalent to 135 respondents, followed by the group whose age ranges between 25 to 35, with a percentage of 5.33%. 45 and more, and it was a very small percentage, reaching -2.67%. The age groups ranging between 35 and 44 reached the youth group. Its rate is 2%.

Table 3. The Distribution of the Sample According to Internet Use

Options	Repetition	Percentage
Always	79	52,66%
Sometimes	60	40%
Scarcely	11	7,34%
Total	150	100%

Through the statistics shown in the table, we conclude that 52.66% are those who regularly use the Internet, i.e. The equivalent of 79 respondents. This explains the freedom to use it in all fields, which increases the possibility of

their exposure to advertisements electronic, followed by 40% of Internet users sometimes for certain circumstances, while there is a small category, Uses the Internet rarely, 7.34%.

Table 4. The Extent of Demand for Electronic Advertisements

Options	Repetition	Percentage
Always	20	13.33%
Sometimes	79	52.67%
Scarcely	51	34%
Total	150	100%

Based on the data contained in the table, it appears that the majority of respondents sometimes accept electronic advertisements. A percentage of 52.66%, which is equivalent to 79 respondents, i.e. according to necessity. On the other hand, we find a percentage of 34% who rarely accept on electronic advertisements, while we find that 13.33% permanently accept advertisements, electronic.

Table 5. The Sample's Most Preferred Types of Electronic Advertisements

Options	Repetition	Percentage
Commodity advertisements	37	24.67%
Service advertisements	57	38%
Both together	56	37.33%
Total	150	100%

By reading the table, we notice that most of the respondents prefer service advertisements, which was 38%.

This is the equivalent of 57 respondents, followed by advertisements for both at a rate of 37.33%, which is equivalent to 57 respondents, while we find, the remaining category that is interested in commodity advertisements is estimated at 37 respondents, or 24.66%, and this is due to the nature of the market and the needs of each group.

Table 6. The Most Commonly Used Medium for Exposure to Electronic Advertisements

Options	Repetition	Percentage
Computer	53	35.33%
The Phone	76	50.67%
Electronic panel	21	14%
Total	150	100%

The table data indicate that the mobile phone is the primary medium through which one is exposed to advertisements. Electronic at a rate of 50.66%, equivalent to 76 respondents, due to the presence of a large percentage who own mobile devices, whether followed by the percentage of computer users, which was estimated at 53 respondents, or 35.33%. As for the last category used, For the electronic panel, it was small, estimated at 14%, equivalent to 21 respondents, and this is due to the modernity of the method.

Table 7. The Number of Respondents Who View Advertisements for Food Products

Options	Repetition	Percentage
Always	43	28.66%
Sometimes	81	54%
Scarcely	26	17.34%
Total	150	100%

Through our reading of the table, we notice that the majority of respondents view advertisements for food products occasionally, with a percentage of 54%, which is equivalent to 81 respondents, and this is due to the presence of advertisements for multiple other competing products, followed by a percentage 28.66% who answered always Equivalent to 26 respondents. A That is equivalent to 43 respondents, while 17.33% responded rarely.

Table 8. The Extent to Which Colleagues are Invited to Follow Advertisements of Food Product Companies

Options	Repetition	Percentage
Yes	90	60%
No	60	40%
Total	150	100%

Through the data contained in the table, it is clear that the majority of respondents invite colleagues to follow advertisements, Food products, estimated at 90 respondents, i.e. 60%, while the rest of the respondents answered 40%, i.e. Equivalent to 60 respondents.

Table 9. The Most Commonly Used Advertising Method for Following Up on Advertisements for Food Product Companies

Options	Repetition	Percentage
Radio	6	4%
TV	63	42%
Internet and Social Networking Sites	81	54%
Total	150	100%

From the table data, it is clear that the Internet and social networking sites are the most widely used means

To follow up on the advertisements of food production establishments, it was estimated at 81 respondents, or 54%, then followed by television. By 42%, equivalent to 63 respondents, then followed in last place by radio, by 4%, equivalent to 6 respondents. This means that most of the respondents pay attention to the Internet and social networking sites.

Table 10. The Motivations Behind Electronic Advertisements for Food Manufacturing Establishments to Compare Their Products

Options	Repetition	Percentage
Yes	84	56%
No	66	44%
Total	150	100%

From the data contained in the table, it is clear that most of the respondents are motivated by electronic advertisements for institutions, Food production compared between the products of different institutions, and this was 56%, equivalent to 84% Researched: This is due to the presence of institutions that publish advertisements with attractive designs and different types, which creates a desire to. Comparison: While the remaining group answered no, it was estimated at 66 respondents, or 44%.

Table 11. The Duration of the Electronic Advertisement's Content

Options	Repetition	Percentage
Short	36	24%
Medium	99	66%
Long	15	10%
Total	150	100%

Through observation of the gondola, we see that most of the researchers keep the content of electronic advertising technically sound. Studying for a medium-term study is 66% of those studied, followed by 24% of those studied.

The number of researchers who maintain electronic advertising is 15% of us. Here we explain that most individuals remain content with copying electronic, their memory for a long time.

Table 12. The Extent to Which Electronic Advertisements Rely on Seductive Methods

Options	Repetition	Percentage
Yes	126	84%
Item Shape	71	47.34%
Visual Effects	45	30%
Celebrity hiring	10	6.66%
No	24	16%
Total	150	100%

From the data received in the gondola field, it is clear that the majority of researchers understand the meaning of electronic advertising. It relies on seductive methods at a rate of 84%, which is equivalent to 126 students, while most of the

students are, with a percentage of 47.33%, which of us is equivalent to 71 of the research conducted by Ban Shankal on the commodity, this is the method most commonly used technically? Advertisements, in order to attract the customer and his temptations. Haneen expressed this to some of the researchers on electronic advertising. It depends on visual influences at a rate of 30%, which is equivalent to 45 subjects. As for the last category, we stated, at a small percentage, it reached 6.66%. Which of us is equivalent to 10 publicly stated that electronic advertisements depend on, on hiring celebrities. On the other hand, the respondents expressed their opinion that electronic advertisements should not rely on seductive methods, with a percentage reaching, to 16%, which is equivalent to 24 respondents.

Table 13. The Extent to Which Electronic Advertisements are Sufficient to Push Customers to Learn about the Company's Products

Options	Repetition	Percentage
Yes	57	38%
Mostly yes	90	60%
No	3	2%
Total	150	100%

Through our reading of the table, it becomes clear that most of the respondents answered that electronic advertisements are somewhat sufficient to pay, Customers to learn about the products by 60%, which is equivalent to 90 respondents, while another group answered yes, estimated at 57 respondents, i.e. 38%. As for the last category, they responded with a very small percentage of 2%, equivalent to 3 respondents.

Table 14. Good Design of Electronic Advertisements Generates a Desire to Buy the Advertised

Options	Repetition	Percentage
Yes	136	90.66%
No	14	9.34%
Total	150	100%

From the data in the table, it is clear that most of the respondents believe that good design of electronic advertising generates desire, refer to the universe of electronic advertisements 136 respondents, i.e. 90.66%, of purchasing the advertised product said: "This well- designed product attracts attention," while the other category responded by 9.34%, i.e. 14 respondents.

Table 15. The Multiplicity and Diversity of Electronic Advertisements Provides the Opportunity to Choose the Appropriate Product

Options	Repetition	Percentage
Yes	50	33.34%
Sometimes	96	64%
Scarcely	4	2.66%
Total	150	100%

From the data contained in the table, it is clear that a large percentage of the respondents, estimated at 64%, which is equivalent to what 96 respondents believe that the multiplicity and diversity of electronic advertisements sometimes provides the opportunity to choose the appropriate product, while 33.34%, equivalent to 50 respondents, stated that the multiplicity and diversity of electronic advertisements always provides the opportunity to choose the product. appropriate among many products, while 2.66%, equivalent to 4 respondents, expressed that the number and diversity, Electronic advertisements rarely provide the opportunity to choose the appropriate product, and in general, the results of the table indicate that the number of, the diversity of electronic advertisements provides the opportunity to choose the appropriate product that meets their desires and needs.

Conclusion

Through research, it becomes clear to us the effective role that advertising plays in the organization. The reality of intense competition that it lives in, Institutions and the constant desire to obtain a share of the market that enables them to survive and continue is a

necessity Carrying out advertising activity and bearing its costs, with the aim of achieving specific and planned results whose effects will be reflected in the future, Or sooner, the product will be accepted in the market and increase its sales, and this can only be achieved through successful planning of advertising campaigns. And develop appropriate pricing policies and strategies that take into account the conditions of each company and market. However, the quality of the product and the mechanism remain, with the target segment of customers, it plays an essential role in keeping the market share resilient marketing and depth of relationship challenges. Through the results recorded in the research tables, the following was reached:

1. Through the results of Table 3, it was shown that customers accept electronic advertisements.
2. Customers are exposed to electronic advertisements through various media, and this has been proven by the results of Tables 7-9.
3. Advertising affects customers' attitudes towards products, and this has been proven through the results of Tables 10-12.
4. Advertising helps increase sales, and this has been proven by the results of Tables 13-15.

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